

TOWARDS EPISTEMIC INCLUSIVITY

Paola Di Maio, December 2020

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Inspired by an invitation to contribute to a collaborative paper from Camille Maumet et al at OHBM-OSR, on the topic of how to increase participation and inclusivity in research conferences
Towards more inclusive online conferences, Dec 1, Google docs

The notion of Epistemic inclusivity was initially contributed (see email)
Due to word limits of the initial submission it was not possible to elaborate muc.
This research note therefore is a shared draft to initiate collaboration around this novel concept

EPISTEMIC inclusivity
Paola Di Maio, via OHBM- OSR, Dec 2020

Epistemic democracy is a relatively new paradigm, by now is fairly well understood
<https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/full/10.1146/annurev-polisci-110113-121908>

Applied to research and science, epistemic/epistemological democracy refers to inclusivity research policies that support lines of enquiry open to multiple perspectives, theories and hypotheses

Therefore the concept of epistemic inclusivity in science can be defined as **inquiry that is open to a multiplicity of theories and hypotheses to be formulated, and does not exclude research design and experiments not following a dominant theory or scientific paradigm**

Semantic inclusivity refers to the choice of axioms and languages, provided their encoding is explicit, thus that can be explained and justified, even when not conforming to a choice of language dictated by the established institutional culture

Finally, inclusivity must be aimed at reducing bias deriving from adherence to a single epistemological stance and language, driven by established institution, however it should also not introduce new types of research bias and should be objectively verifiable

Please elaborate!

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